

Some Heteroptera (Hemiptera) Species that are potential natural enemies of *Cimex quadrimaculata* (Müller, 1766) (Hymenoptera: Cimbicidae)

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ABSTRACT: The study was carried out in the provinces of Elazığ and Diyarbakir between 2020-2021. In the studies conducted in nature and in laboratory conditions, it is observed that the species does not feed on advanced larval stages of the pest. From the species identified in the study, *Deraeocoris trifasciatus* Linnaeus, 1767 and *Globiceps sphaegiformis* Rossi, 1790 species belonging to the Miridae family were observed in nature, and *Nagusta goedelii* Kolenati, 1857 and *Zelus (Diplodacus) renardii* (Kolenati, 1856) species belonging to the Reduviidae family were observed to in laboratory conditions to feed on the pest. *Geocoris luridus* Fieber, 1844 and *Geocoris putonianus* Bergroth, 1892 species belonging to the Geocoridae family were found to be abundant in nature before the pest began to be observed in nature. *Brachycoleus steini* Jakovlev, 1884 specimens and *Macrotylus ponticus* Seidenstücker, 1966 found in abundance in the garden at the larval period of pest of these species.

It has not been determined that they feed on pests. All species have been detected in the fauna of both provinces. These species are also the first record for the provinces where they have been found.

KEYWORDS: Almond, *Cimex quadrimaculata*, Natural Enemies, Predator.

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INTRODUCTION

The Cimbicidae is a small family, with 196 species occurring in the World (Özbek, 2014). In Turkey; There were a 23 species (Önder, 2011). *Cimex quadrimaculata*

(Müller, 1766) is an important pest in fruit-growing areas that especially on almonds of Turkey (Bolu, 2016) (Figure 1). *C. quadrimaculata* was very serious pest on young almond plants (Özbek,

2014; Çakıcı et al., 2015). When this pest is not methodological managed, it creates significant damage of many fruits.

Additionally; There is no licensed chemical control recommended against to this species. Therefore, its biological control is an opportunity. Özgen et al. (2010) obtained *Listrognathus mactator* (Thunberg) (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Cryptinae) as a parasitoid of *C. quadrimaculata* for the first time. Özbek (2014) obtained

Opheltes glaucopterus (Linnaeus) and *Phobetes nigriceps* (Gravenhorst) (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Ctenopelmatinae), as larva – pupa parasitoids of *C. quadrimaculata*. *P. nigriceps* was obtained for the first time from *C. quadrimaculata* larvae. No any studies have been conducted on the predator species of this species. The aim of the study is to determine the predator species belonging to the Heteroptera order of the pest.

Figure 1. The habitus of *Cimbex quadrimaculata* larvae and feeding on almond trees.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The present study was carried out in Elazığ and Diyarbakır provinces in Anatolia Region of Turkey in 2021-2022. The studies were carried out between 03.05.2021 and 15.06.2021 in Diyarbakır, Egil and Elazığ province and Keban district. Studies were carried out in a climate cabinet with 65% humidity and $25\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperature conditions (Figure 2). When the larvae started to appear in nature, 50 1st instar larvae

were collected and brought to the laboratory and left to feed on almond leaves in culture plates. Species that have been found to feed in nature and the biological periods of the pest have been recorded. Miridae species could not be brought alive from natural conditions to laboratory conditions, while Reduviidae species brought from nature were left in the same environment as pests with culture plates. It has been observed that some species insert their stylets into the pest.

Figure 2 a) Climate Cabinet b) Containers with *Cimbex quadrimaculata* larvae and pupa.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Following 8 species were found in the *C. quadrimaculata* research conducted in two localities in Elazığ and Diyarbakır (Table 1)

Table 1. Heteroptera species, Localities and Biological Observations

Family	Species	Locality	Biological Stage of <i>Cimex quadrimaculata</i> larvae fed by the predator (*Field and laboratory, **Field,***Potential)
MIRIDAE	<i>Brachycoleus steini</i> Jakovlev, 1884	Diyarbakır, Eğil, Elazığ, Keban	No feeding (Abundant)
MIRIDAE	<i>Deraeocoris trifasciatus</i> ** Linnaeus, 1767	Diyarbakır, Eğil, Elazığ, Keban	1st instar larvae
MIRIDAE	<i>Globiceps sphaegiformis</i> ** Rossi, 1790	Diyarbakır, Eğil, Elazığ, Keban	1 instar larvae
MIRIDAE	<i>Macrotylus ponticus</i> Seidenstücker, 1966	Diyarbakır, Eğil, Elazığ, Keban	No feeding (Abundant)
REDUVIIDAE	<i>Nagusta goedelii</i> * Kolenati, 1857	Diyarbakır, Eğil, Elazığ, Keban	1st instar larvae.
REDUVIIDAE	<i>Zelus (Diplodacus) renardii</i> * (Kolenati, 1856)	Diyarbakır, Eğil	1st instar larvae.
GECORIDAE	<i>Geocoris luridus</i> *** Fieber, 1844	Diyarbakır, Eğil, Elazığ, Keban	Before the pest occurred in nature, it was observed in each orchards in many amounts.
GECORIDAE	<i>Geocoris putonianus</i> *** Bergroth, 1892	Diyarbakır, Eğil, Elazığ, Keban	Before the pest occurred in nature, it was observed in each orchards in many amounts.

The species has been seen during the months of March and July. They are abundant in the egg and larval stage of the pest (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Dates of Predator Species in Nature

Species belonging to the Miridae family were observed in field conditions where they were fed in the first larval stage of the pest. Since the species belonging to this family could not be brought to the laboratory. conditions alive, the culture plate feeding experiments could not be conducted. In these species; *Globiceps sphaegiformis* Rossi, 1790 was determined in the provinces of Elazığ and Diyarbakır in previous years (Matocq et al., 2014; Özgen and Dioli, 2019). There are no studies on the food preferences of the species belonging to this genus. Kiyak (2020); reported that *Deraeocoris* spp. is zoophytophagous, generally feeding on aphids and it preys on eggs of true bugs, larvae of whiteflies. However, there is no record of it feeding on the Hymenoptera species. On the other hand; *Zelus (Diplodacus) renardii* (Kolenati, 1856) and *Nagusta goedelii* (Kolenati, 1857) species collected from the field and brought to the laboratory were fed with the first larval stage of the pest. These species stand out as the polyphagous predator. Çelik et al., 2021; reported that this species is fed on *Allantus* (s.str.) *viennensis* (Schrank, 1781) in Diyarbakır. *N. goedelii* was generalist predator potentially capable of attacking the eggs and first instar nymphs of some Pentatomidae specimens and gypsy moth (*Lymantria dispar* (Linnaeus, 1758), Lepidoptera (Erebidae) (Bigsby et al., 2011; Bulgarini et al., 2020). The feeding record on this species is the first. *Geocoris* spp. are among the most important predaceous insects in the world. They feed on eggs and small larvae of most lepidopteran pests. Moreover, *Geocoris* sp. species were found to be abundant in almond trees in gardens where they formed a population before the pest began to appear in nature. In studies conducted in nature and laboratory conditions, it was found that the species did not feed on the advanced larval periods of the pest. All species have been detected in the fauna of both provinces. These species are also the first record for the provinces where they have been found. It has been observed

that *Zelus (Diplodacus) renardii* and *Nagusta goedelii* Kolenati, 1857 species do not feed on the biological periods of the pest after the 2nd larval period. For *Brachycoleus steini*; The presence of the *Centaurea* sp. plant in the garden edges has also increased the probability of this species being found in almond trees. Abundant varieties of this plant in this species in the literature are supportive (Hosseini, 2016). Phytophagous status in *Macrotylus* species should be investigated.

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Figures 2. The Figures of Heteroptera Species in Almond Orchards. A: *Globiceps sphaegiformis* Rossi, 1790; B: *Deraeocoris trifasciatus* Linnaeus, 1767; C: *Geocoris* sp. nymph, D: *Nagusta goedelii* Kolenati, 1857; E: *Geocoris putonianus* Bergroth, 1892 (Çerçi and Özgen, 2021); F: *Macrotylus ponticus* Seidenstücker, 1966.